

NOVEL BIOPOLYMER COMPOSITES BASED ON WS₂ INORGANIC NANOTUBES

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this investigation is to highlight the latest findings on the use of tungsten disulphide (WS₂) inorganic nanotubes in the development of novel biopolymer composite materials with enhanced thermal and mechanical properties. Particular interest has been devoted to the analysis of the influence of INT-WS₂ on the structure, morphology and properties of biodegradable and renewable thermoplastics, such as poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (PHB), poly(hydroxybutyrate-co-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) and poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA). Recent results have raised new expectations, since it has been observed that well-dispersed INT-WS₂ exhibit a much more prominent nucleation activity, improving the overall crystallization process of PHB and PHBV than specific nucleating agents or other reported nano-sized fillers, such as carbon nanotubes and graphene. Similarly, good dispersion and interfacial adhesion of INT-WS₂ in a PLLA matrix significantly influence the (poor) crystallizability of PLLA. These features may be advantageous for the enhancement of the mechanical properties and processability of this new class of WS₂-based composite materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, research interest in the field of thermoplastic composites has moved from “high-performance” advanced materials towards the development of “cost-performance” engineering composites. In particular, thermoplastic-based composites reinforced with tungsten or molybdenum disulfide (WS₂ or MoS₂) inorganic fullerene-like nanoparticles (IFs) and nanotubes (INTs) have been shown to offer design, processing, performance, and cost advantages when compared to carbon nanotubes, nanoclays or other inorganic nanoparticles, for manufacturing advanced structural parts by simple melt-processing routes without the need for modifiers or surfactants [1, 2]. The surprising properties of these layered metal dichalcogenides such as high impact resistance and superior tribological behavior open up a wide variety of opportunities for applications in, for example, the automotive and aerospace industries, electronics and medical technology [3, 4] and, more particularly, in the field of polymer nanocomposites [1, 2]. The needle-like structure and specific surface chemistry of WS₂ result in uniform dispersion and favorable INT-polymer interfacial interaction, these characteristics together with nanosize and unique mechanical behavior of INTs endow the polymer composites with these INTs enhanced mechanical and thermal properties. The property improvements generated by these nanostructures have also resulted in their synergetic use with other organic micro-particles (nucleating agents), micro-fibers (carbon fibers) or nanofillers (carbon nanotubes) to tailor

more sophisticated hybrid materials with complex architectures, interactions, morphology and functionality [1].

The first synthesis of tungsten disulphide (WS_2) fullerene-like nanoparticles and nanotubes in thermally sulfurized tungsten films was reported by Tenne et al. in 1992 and 1993 [5, 6]. Since then, the synthetic technology has advanced considerably and almost pure materials (>99%) are now available at industrial scales [7, 8]. The synthetic process is catalyst-free, and the precursors (eg. tungsten oxide and H_2S or sulfur) are relatively inexpensive. Moreover, INT- WS_2 are low-cost, environmentally friendly and biocompatible nanofillers since they possess a much lower cytotoxicity than other nanoparticles, such as silica or carbon black [9]. Promising results have also been recently found with respect to the biocompatibility of INT(IF)- WS_2 with salivary gland cells, rendering them attractive for several technological and biomedical applications [10]. An exciting opportunity exists for research in the area of nanocomposite polymer biomaterials. In this respect, WS_2 nanotubes have been used as reinforcing agents to improve the thermal, mechanical and tribological properties of PHB [11], PLLA [12], poly(ether ether ketone) (PEEK) [13] and poly(propylene fumarate) (PPF) employed in bone tissue engineering [14].

There is growing interest in developing bio-based polymers and innovative process technologies that can reduce the dependence on fossil fuel and move to a sustainable materials basis. The many advantages of bio-plastics such as 100% biodegradable, produced from natural renewable resources, able to be recycled, reused, composted or burned without producing toxic byproducts, which make them an excellent alternative to traditional plastic products. Unfortunately for certain applications, biopolyesters (e.g. PHB, PLLA, etc.) cannot be fully competitive with conventional thermoplastics since some of their properties have been until now too weak. Therefore, to extend their applications, these biopolymers have been formulated and associated with nano-sized fillers, which could bring a large range of improved properties (stiffness, permeability, crystallinity, thermal stability) [15, 16]. They thus represent a strong and emerging answer for improved and eco-friendly materials. The objective of this work is to emphasize the most recent findings about the influence of INT- WS_2 on the structure, morphology and properties of the aforementioned thermoplastics (PHB, PHBV, PLLA). Particular interest has been devoted to explore an alternative strategy to improve the crystallizability of these biopolymer materials based on the incorporation of small amounts of INT- WS_2 . These observations will enable the development of novel biopolymer nanocomposites with improved thermal and mechanical properties for many eco-friendly (e.g. packaging) and biomedical (e.g. surgical sutures, bone fixation devices, etc.) applications.

2 PREPARATION AND DISPERSION OF WS_2 INORGANIC NANOTUBES

Nanoparticles have a much higher surface-to-volume ratio than conventional micron-sized particles, and with decreasing particle size the number of molecules/atoms present on the surface increases enormously. As a consequence, interparticle attraction through forces such as van der Waals and electrostatic forces, as well as magnetic attraction, becomes stronger resulting in a high surface energy and a tendency to agglomerate during melt blending. To reach high performance and possible commercial success for the polymer nanocomposites, even at a low nanoparticle content, the key factors to be considered include the availability of cost-effective nanoparticles with the proper inherent properties and optimised nanoparticle dispersion, interface chemistry and nanoscale morphology. Accordingly, much research on polymer-based nanocomposites has been performed, initially with interesting observations involving exfoliated clays and more recent studies with carbon nanotubes, exfoliated graphite (graphene) and a host of other nanoscale inorganic filler or fiber modifications [15, 16].

Recent works with IF/INT- WS_2 have raised new expectations, since it has been observed in a number of polymer systems that these nanostructures can be efficiently dispersed in the polymer matrix using the most simple, cost-effective and ecologically friendly melt processing techniques. As an example, WS_2 inorganic nanotubes were introduced into a biopolymer (PLLA) matrix by melt-mixing of using a micro-extruder (Thermo-Haake Minilab system) operated at 190 °C and a rotor speed of 100 rpm for 10 min, Figure 1a. The image shows an overview of a fractured surface of a PLLA/INT- WS_2 nanocomposite with 1.0 wt.% of INT- WS_2 . It can be clearly seen that the processing

of the PLLA/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites was effective with the INTs uniformly dispersed at the nanoscale in the PLLA matrix by the shear force encountered during melt-blending [12]. Promising INT-WS₂ have also been successfully integrated into poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (PHB) matrix, as one of the most extensively researched and utilized biodegradable and renewable thermoplastic polyester, using a simple solution blending method (Figure 1b). The WS₂ inorganic nanotubes do not require exfoliation or modification, making it possible to obtain advanced nanocomposite materials without the complexity and processing cost associated to these treatments [11]. In the same way, a series of biopolymer PHBV/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites have been prepared at various INT-WS₂ loadings ranging from 0.1 to 1.0 wt.%, without the use of surface modifiers.

Figure 1. High-resolution SEM image of biopolymer nanocomposites containing 1.0 wt.% INT-WS₂: (a) PLLA and (b) PHB

3 CRYSTALLIZATION AND MELTING BEHAVIOUR

The major issue in expanding commercial opportunities for PLLA, PHB and related polymer materials (PHBV) is their crystallization behavior [16, 17]. Incorporating well-dispersed nanoparticles like INT-WS₂ into biopolymer can modify the crystallization behavior. Therefore, it is of great interest to investigate the nucleation, crystallization, and structural development of the matrix in INT-reinforced biopolymer materials. This would help to optimize the manufacturing conditions in order to obtain high-performance nanocomposites and to fully exploit their potential in practical applications.

The non-isothermal melt-crystallization of neat PHB and its nanocomposites at different INTs loadings was investigated by DSC using a Perkin Elmer DSC7/Pyris differential scanning calorimeter. Prior to cooling, the samples were held at 190 °C for 5 minutes to erase the thermal history of PHB. Different crystallization experiments were performed by varying the cooling rates (e.g. 2-20 °C/min). As an example, Figure 2 shows the dynamic crystallization exotherms for neat PHB and three nanocomposites, obtained during cooling at 10 °C/min from the melt state, where it can be observed that the crystallization temperature peak (T_p) is affected by the presence of the INT-WS₂. This effect was clearly a function of composition, showing a remarkable increase of T_p of around 35 °C for the PHB nanocomposite with 0.1 wt.% of INT-WS₂. At higher INT-WS₂ content the value of T_p for PHB continues to rise and tends to stabilize for the higher concentrations of 0.5 and 1.0 wt.%, with increments of around 37 °C. Figure 2 also summarizes the variation of T_p with INT-WS₂ loadings for PHBV/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites. It is obvious that the values of T_p for the nanocomposites are always higher than that of the neat PHB and PHBV at the same cooling rate, indicating that the presence of INT-WS₂ plays a dominant role in accelerating the crystallization of PHB and PHBV due to a heterogeneous nucleation effect in the nanocomposites. Subsequent melting behaviour of PHB/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites was studied systematically by considering the effects of the INT-WS₂ loadings and cooling rates. At higher cooling rates, double melting peaks were observed both for PHB and PHBV/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites, which were caused by recrystallization during the heating process. In particular, it was found that increasing the INT-WS₂ loadings and decreasing the cooling rates would restrict the occurrence of the recrystallization of PHB in the nanocomposites. In the same way, the addition of INTs also results in noticeable variations of the T_p of PHBV, showing similar trends

to those observed from the PHB cooling thermograms (Figure 2). In this case, the samples were melted at 180 °C and kept at this temperature for 5 minutes to prevent any matrix degradation. The presence of INT-WS₂ influenced the crystallization process of PHBV leading to increases in the crystallization rates. As a result increased crystallization temperatures are observed. For example, at cooling rate of 10 °C/min, $T_{p, \text{PHBV}} = 88.0$ °C, $T_{p, 0.1 \text{ wt.}\%} = 100.4$ °C, $T_{p, 0.5 \text{ wt.}\%} = 107.4$ °C, and $T_{p, 1.0 \text{ wt.}\%} = 112.4$ °C. The data clearly shows that the addition of INT-WS₂ plays a remarkable role in accelerating the crystallization rate of PHBV. Nevertheless, for the same nanofiller loading, the improvements in T_p for the PHBV-based samples are lower than those observed for the corresponding binary PHB-INT nanocomposites.

Figure 2. DSC thermograms of the dynamic crystallization of biopolymer/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites obtained during cooling at 10 °C/min.

Degree of crystallinity is also an important index for the characterization of crystallization properties of materials. The results obtained from the DSC analysis show that the cooling rate and INT-WS₂ content are very efficient factors for the control of crystallinity $(1-\lambda)_c$ of PHB and PHBV. Similar to the results shown in Figure 2, the addition of INT-WS₂ induces an increase in the average $(1-\lambda)_c$ value of PHB in the nanocomposites up to 17-21% with respect to neat PHB ($(1-\lambda)_{c, \text{PHB}} = 51\%$). The data reflects that this increment appears to be slightly dependent on the concentration of INT-WS₂. These changes occur without modifying the orthorhombic crystalline structure of PHB in the nanocomposites, as shown by wide-angle X-ray diffraction (WAXS) and infrared/Raman spectroscopy [11].

In order to put this into perspective the nucleating capacity of INT-WS₂ was compared with that of other PHB-based composite materials reported in the literature incorporating nucleating agents (NA) for PHB, such as talc, boron nitride (BN), melamine, thiamine, cyclodextrin (α -CD) and lignin carbon nanotubes, graphene, etc. where the nanosized fillers were shown to have the added advantage of acting as reinforcements for the polymer. Figure 3 compares the crystallization behavior observed for the PHB/INT-WS₂ composites with that of PHB containing similar amounts (1.0 wt.%) of nucleating agents and/or nano-sized reinforcements. The crystallization behavior was determined from the exothermic DSC curves obtained at 10 °C/min by analyzing the difference between the crystallization peak temperature (T_p) of the composite and that of the neat PHB matrix (ΔT_p). The value of $\Delta T_p \approx 36$ °C obtained for non-modified INT-WS₂ is higher than that of 32 °C observed for BN, and far exceeds the values observed for other promising nanofillers such as carboxyl-functionalized multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) and graphene oxide (GO) [11]. In the same way, incorporating 1.0 wt.% INT-WS₂ effectively increased the T_p of PHBV to a value comparable to that of BN, and greater than all other NAs (Figure 3). BN is currently estimated to be more expensive than INT-WS₂ and, like talc, is not a nanoparticle filler, also possibly leading to deficient mechanical reinforcement qualities that are observed with other nano-sized filler materials [18]. Whilst the available literature on NA for

PHBV is relatively limited, the data presented here shows that non-modified INT-WS₂ is one of the best alternatives currently available.

Figure 3. Increment in the crystallization temperature peak (ΔT_p) of PHB and PHBV systems containing different kinds of fillers obtained during cooling at 10 °C/min.

In addition to the above observation, polarized optical microscopy (POM) was used to visually examine the crystalline morphology of PHBV and the nanocomposites, in particular their spherulitic structure (Figure 4). Neat PHBV and (particularly) the 0.1 wt.% samples showed ring-banded spherulites with concentric bands and Maltese-crosses after cooling to room temperature at 10 °C/min [18]. However, the increase of concentration of INT-WS₂ (0.5 wt.%) clearly disturbed spherulite formation, possibly due to the dramatic increase of the nucleation density and faster crystal formation of PHBV.

Figure 4. POM images of neat PHBV and PHBV/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites obtained at room temperature after cooling from the melt at 10°C/min.

The goal of the next study is to investigate the effectiveness of the use of small amounts of INT-WS₂ to improve the crystallizability of PLLA biopolymer. In particular, the role of the INT-WS₂ concentration on the cold-crystallization and melting behaviour of PLLA will be discussed from a kinetic point of view. Although PLLA is semicrystalline, it has poor crystallizability and is usually found in the amorphous state due to poor chain segment mobility that prevents the formation of stable nuclei and the growth of lamellae. As global research is moving towards the diversification of PLA-based products, it is necessary to enhance their crystallization behavior in order to achieve required thermal and mechanical properties as well as industrial scale processability.

It is well-known that the crystallization of isotropic polymers by heating above the glass transition temperature (T_g) is denominated cold-crystallization. Unlike melt crystallization, in which the motion of polymer chains can be carried out entirely via molecular reptation, the polymer chains in the rubbery state complete the corresponding conformational rearrangements via cooperative segmental movements. As a result, the crystal structure and morphology obtained from cold-crystallization may

be expected to differ from that obtained by melt-crystallization. Figure 5a shows the DSC melting thermograms for PLLA/INT-WS₂ (1.0 wt.%) recorded at heating rates of 1, 2, 5, 10 and 20 °C/min after rapid cooling from 225 °C at 40 °C/min. The T_{cc} values of neat PLLA and its nanocomposites at various heating rates were also plotted in Figure 5a. It is necessary to note that PLLA manifests slow crystallization on cooling from the melt. It does not apparently crystallize if it is cooled at a rate of 20 °C/min or faster [12]. The results obtained clearly show that both heating rate and INT-WS₂ loading are the two main factors that affected the non-isothermal cold-crystallization behaviour of PLLA in the nanocomposites. With increasing heating rate, the crystallization exotherms became broader, and the cold-crystallization peak temperature (T_{cc}) shifted to higher temperature. Moreover, at a given heating rate (for example, 10 °C/min), T_{cc} for neat PLLA was 99.9 °C, whereas T_{cc} for 0.1, 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% were found to be 98.6, 94.7, and 95.6 °C, respectively, showing a general shift to lower temperatures with increasing INT-WS₂ content in the nanocomposites (Figure 5a). Such results indicate that the incorporation of INT-WS₂ enhanced the non-isothermal cold-crystallization of PLLA matrix, to a degree that was strongly dependent on the INT-WS₂ content.

Figure 5 (a) DSC melting thermograms of PLLA/INT-WS₂ (1.0 wt.%) recorded at indicated heating rates after rapid cooling at 40 °C/min and (b) variation of the melting crystallinity $(1-\lambda)_m$ of PLLA/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites with heating rate; inset is the difference between the overall crystallinity change derived from the difference between endotherm and exotherm, $\Delta(1-\lambda) = (1-\lambda)_m - (1-\lambda)_{cc}$, for PLLA/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites.

On subsequent heating, double-melting peaks for PLLA/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites can be attributed to a melt-recrystallization mechanism [19]. The data presented in Figure 5b shows the difference between the overall crystallinity change derived from the difference between endotherm and exotherm, $\Delta(1-\lambda) = (1-\lambda)_m - (1-\lambda)_{cc}$, for neat PLLA and its nanocomposites, which can be used to highlight the recrystallization ability of the PLLA crystals. At lower $\Delta(1-\lambda)$, the reorganization of the PLLA crystals is more difficult. The quantitative analysis showed that increasing the heating rate can effectively inhibit the reorganization process of PLLA, and further increasing the INT-WS₂ concentration led to a marked influence on the recrystallization of PLLA, especially when at low cooling rates.

4 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Dynamic mechanical tests over a wide range of temperature and frequency are especially sensitive to all kinds of transitions and relaxation processes of the matrix and also to the morphology of the nanocomposites. An analysis of the storage modulus and $\tan \delta$ curves is very useful in predicting the performance of a sample under stress and temperature. The influence of the inorganic nanotubes on the dynamic mechanical behavior of biopolymer/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites has also been investigated [12, 13]. In particular, it was observed that the incorporation of INT-WS₂ produces higher improvements in the degradation temperature, storage modulus, thermal expansion coefficient, hardness, coefficient of friction and wear resistance of the biopolymer (PEEK) than the addition of other inorganic nanofillers (SiO₂, Al₂O₃, SiC, Si₃N₄) or carbon nanotubes [13]. At 25 °C, the modulus

of neat PEEK is 3.9 GPa, and increases by 6, 18 and 30% upon addition of 0.1, 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% INT-WS₂, respectively, pointing out the remarkable stiffening effect of these inorganic nanotubes. For nanofiller contents ≥ 0.5 wt.%, the improvements in storage modulus attained are higher than those reported for PEEK nanocomposites incorporating spherical IF-WS₂ nanoparticles. As known, the shape, size, state of dispersion of the filler and its interfacial adhesion with the matrix strongly influence the properties of the resulting nanocomposites [13]. On the other hand, the incorporation of higher INT-WS₂ contents results in a significant increase in glass transition (T_g) of PEEK, by about 10 °C at 1.0 wt.% loading, indicating that these rigid inorganic nanotubes act effectively as a barrier for the mobility of chain segments in the amorphous region. This also suggests the existence of strong filler-matrix interactions, since the T_g is very sensitive to interfacial interactions between the polymer and the reinforcements. In the same way, the incorporation of INT-WS₂ into the PLLA matrix led to an increase in storage modulus throughout the entire temperature range tested. For example, the value of storage modulus for PLLA (3127 MPa) obtained at room temperature increases to 3630, 3640 and 3590 MPa, respectively, on increasing the INT-WS₂ content from 0.1 to 1.0 wt.%. The presence of INT-WS₂ also induced a decrease in the intensity of $\tan \delta$, indicating that the nanofiller imposes some restrictions on the mobility of the PLLA chain segments. No detectable variation in peak positions PLLA/INTs are observed with the change of composition [12].

The nanohardness (H) and Young's modulus (E) of the PHB/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites have also been investigated using nanoindentation tests [11]. It was found that the nanohardness and Young's modulus of PHB were increased in the nanocomposites. For example, by adding only 0.1 wt.% of INT-WS₂ the Young's modulus of PHB (≈ 6 GPa) increased by 17%. However, this increment remained unchanged with increasing nanofiller concentrations. This trend is also apparent in the hardness variation but the increments in H ($H_{\text{PHB}} = 3.6$ GPa) in the nanocomposites with 0.1, 0.5 and 1.0 wt.% INT-WS₂ are noticeably lower (2-10%). The increase in hardness and modulus may arise from the deformation resistance induced by the INTs as a result of the improved crystallinity, reduced spherulite size but could in principle decrease due to interspherulitic cracking.

Poly(propylene fumarate) (PPF) nanocomposites were fabricated at low loading concentrations (0.01 - 0.2 wt.%) of INT-WS₂ towards the fabrication of biodegradable polymeric implants possessing improved mechanical properties (i.e. compressive modulus, compressive yield strength, flexural modulus and flexural yield strength) for bone tissue engineering applications [14]. Mechanical testing (compression and three-point bending) shows a significant enhancement (up to 28-190%) in the mechanical properties (compressive modulus, compressive yield strength, flexural modulus and flexural yield strength) of PPF/INT-WS₂ nanocomposites compared to the neat PPF. In general, the inorganic nanotubes (INT-WS₂) showed mechanical reinforcement better than (up to 127%) or equivalent to that of carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs and MWCNTs). These improvements are related to the chemical composition (inorganic vs. carbon nanomaterials), the presence of functional groups (such as sulfide and oxysulfide) and individual dispersion of the nanomaterials in the PPF matrix (absence of aggregation of the reinforcing agent INT-WS₂) [14].

5 CONCLUSIONS

The use of tungsten disulfide inorganic nanotubes (INT-WS₂) offers the opportunity to produce novel and advanced biopolymer-based nanocomposite materials with excellent nanoparticle dispersion without the need for modifiers or surfactants via conventional blending methods. The overall crystallization rate, final crystallinity, and subsequent melting behaviour of biopolymer matrix (PHB, PHBV or PLLA) were controlled by both the incorporation of INT-WS₂ and the variation of the cooling rate. In particular, it was shown that INT-WS₂ exhibits much more prominent nucleation activity on the crystallization of biopolymer matrix than other specific nucleating agents or nano-sized fillers. The results obtained from the thermal and mechanical experiments, along with the good materials processability, economic and sustainability benefits, encourage further investigations in order to evaluate the full potential of these new bionanocomposites for their potential use in eco-friendly and medical applications.

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